

Aurora Chaser's Guide to HUXt forecast

Dr. Tanya E. Melnik, Christian L. Harris, Margaret Sonnemann, Vincent E. Ledvina, and Dr. Mathew J. Owens

What is HUXt forecast?

<https://research.reading.ac.uk/met-spate/huxt-forecast/>

HUXt (Heliospheric Upwind eXtrapolation with time dependence) is a solar wind model developed by one of the heliophysics teams from University of Reading. It can be used to predict a plasma cloud from the Sun (coronal mass ejection, or CME for short) arrival time and speed as well as to show the forecast uncertainty.

HUXt uses the same CME data, such as speed, source location on the solar surface, and equations as several other CME models. But what HUXt does *differently* is perform these calculations several hundred times to include different conditions the CME can encounter on its way to Earth. These conditions include slower or faster ambient solar wind through which the CME travels. A good analogy is trying to drive across town with or without traffic. HUXt takes into account many different "traffic" scenarios for CMEs coming off the Sun headed towards Earth that may cause the plasma cloud to arrive earlier or later. This technique is called ensemble modeling. The result is a forecast dashboard that looks like this:

How can we use all of these data in aurora chasing?

Here is the breakdown of all the fields in HUXt forecast dashboard:

① Time series of solar wind speed.

What is it?

This plot is the main part of the forecast. Part of the plot in the white area is the predicted solar wind speed with several lines and different shading for probabilities. Gray is the time prior to the forecast, with prior prediction as well as solar wind speed registered by the DSCOVR satellite (shown in red). Real-time DSCOVR data can be a bit unreliable, so it is primarily used for HUXt forecast verification.

The black line on the plot is the predicted CME speed by the Met Office Space Weather Operations Centre. The black dashed line is the solar wind speed without any influence from a CME. The tan line is the median for all the results when different conditions are used for modeling. Shaded areas represent the spread of results for different conditions. They are given in percentiles and coded by different colors. Narrow color bands mean high confidence in the forecast. Wide bands represent low confidence in the forecast.

How do I use this data?

CME arrival time is notoriously difficult to predict with good accuracy. The HUXt forecast can be used to estimate the interval when a CME can be expected to arrive at Earth as well as the speed at the time of arrival. A CME with a faster speed means less travel time as well as a more significant impact. It also translates into a greater probability of aurora shortly after the CME arrives and starts to interact with Earth's magnetic shield (magnetosphere).

② CME arrival probability at Earth.

What is it?

This plot covers the probability of CME arrival(s) at Earth within a certain time window. Each CME is coded by a different color. A broad and low peak to one of these curves means low probability of arrival and low confidence in the arrival time. A narrow and tall peak means high probability of arrival and high confidence in arrival time.

How do I use this data?

This plot helps answer two burning questions about CME forecasting: "When will the CME come?" and "How sure are we that it is coming?" Tall narrow peaks indicate high chances that something is coming. Be ready to watch the solar wind data when the time of arrival is approaching.

③ Table of the Earth-directed CME properties and forecast arrival times/speeds

What is it?

This is a table of all CMEs with a possible Earth-directed component in the HUXt forecast with corresponding color codes and the following CME characteristics: time, speed, location on the map of solar wind, and width. The table lists the percent of modeled results where the CME was forecasted as arriving at Earth (hit %) as well as the estimated arrival time and margin of error (+/-).

How do I use this data?

Look for CMEs with a high probability of arrival. These are a lot more likely to have an impact than low-probability CMEs that may completely miss Earth. Check the predicted time of arrival as well as the interval to start planning for a potential geomagnetic storm. Of course, we never know if a CME has hit us until we detect its signature in satellites at L1, but it is still good to be prepared for action.

④ Summary of the input data.

What is it?

This is a map of solar wind some distance away from, and looking at, the Sun. The map is generated at a distance of 21.5 solar radii, to be exact. This is where the solar wind is assumed to go “supersonic” and is thus a good input for model boundary conditions. This is like taking a roadtrip in your car and using your cruising highway speed to calculate how long it will take for you to arrive at your destination. You wouldn’t use the speed as you accelerate on the onramp since you haven’t reached the cruising speed you will be at for most of your trip. It just so happens that the “onramp” for solar wind is about 21.5 solar radii long. The CME “footprint” is given by the color assigned to that CME in the table seen in ③. CMEs that are no longer in the forecast appear as gray circles. Earth is the dot in the center of the map that may or may not be within the CME circle.

How do I use this data?

Look for CMEs that have Earth within their “footprint”. They are more likely to produce an impact and a resulting geomagnetic disturbance leading to aurora. CMEs with the “footprint” grazing Earth may pass close enough for the magnetosphere to feel the shock and minor impact.

⑤ The probability density of CME arrival speeds, for the Earth-impacting CMEs only.

What is it?

This is a plot of confidence in predicted CME speeds at the time of arrival. Higher confidence levels will be reflected as narrower peaks.

How do I use this data?

Faster CMEs are more likely to have a stronger impact. Look for CMEs with higher speeds and narrow peaks as prime candidates to produce stronger geomagnetic disturbances which can in turn lead to stronger auroral displays.

Just as any other current model, HUXt can not perfectly predict CMEs. Solar wind leaving the Sun has a long way to travel before it arrives at Earth, and current observational or tracking tools do not generate sufficient data for accurate modeling. Any forecast remains a possibility until the CME is detected by one of the space weather satellites at L1 (at Earth). The ground-truth data of aurora also come from live sightings and sky cameras, not from solar wind data at L1. Once a CME hits upstream monitors, it still needs to interact with Earth's magnetosphere which can funnel energy from the solar wind into the aurora through complicated mechanisms outside the scope of a CME model.